

Corporate Social Responsibility impacts sustainable organizational growth (firm performance): An empirical analysis of Pakistan stock exchange-listed firms

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of Organizational sustainable growth (firm performance) on Corporate Social Responsibility, Leverage on Assets, firm age and firm size. This study used sample data of 296 Pakistan stock exchange-listed firms and applied correlation, Ordinary least square regression model to estimate the factor impact, and Robustness test for the result is reliable and sustainable. This study used Sustainable Corporate Social Responsibility (independent variable), leverage on Assets (moderator variable), firm age and firm size (control variable) and Correlation, Ordinary least square regression model that confirmed their variables, i.e. Corporate Social Responsibility, Leverage on Assets, firm age and firm size highly impacting on sustainable organizational growth (firm performance). Robustness test results also confirm the reliability, validity and sustainability of results. That shows results are highly significant, reliable, and sustainable. Sustainable Corporate Social Responsibility is the leading factor that enhances the firm performance. Firm size and age are significant for sustainable organizational growth (firm performance). This study's implication is very significant; policymakers should focus more on Sustainable Corporate Social Responsibility and corporate commitments. Study recommended to firms; developed a sustainable environmental structure: Enhancing the employee's motivation (self-efficacy), performance per-motion bonuses, employee's need and Corporate Social Responsibility leads to sustainable organizational growth (firm performance).
Key Word: Sustainable organizational growth (firm performance), Sustainable Corporate Social Responsibility, Leverage on Assets, Firm Age, Firm Size

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1. Introduction

Sustainable Corporate Performance is the most recent, famous and widespread concept. Markets need and human resources participation in industries is essential; Sustainable Corporate Performance depends on environmental sustainability. Sustainable Corporate Performance is role play in ethical and efficacy of employees for goals and decision-making planning and strategies. Business motives to earn profit and low expenses general way to maximize earning. Some indirect expenses that essential for firms to bear for sustain firm

environment, survival in market competition. One of those expenses is Sustainable Corporate Social Responsibility. Companies for his survival do different mergers, focus research and development, and capture new markets. Achieving so much, but in between the social values and responsibility minimized. To examines the moderating and direct impact between corporate social responsibility and firm performance (Anser, M. K., et al. 2018). Firm's CSR concept was used to measure the relationship with IT-enabled innovation, and its impact on Firm's performance. CSR and IT-